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Enhancing Mechanical Properties of 3D Printed Parts by Spraying Cellulose Nanocrystals

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Delamination: Major Threat to 3D-Printed Structures

Additive manufacturing (AM) has enabled low cost fabrication of parts with complex geometries and minimum waste.

Printed polymers remain too low in strength mainly because of poor interlayer adhesion

Printed ABS after Short Beam Test

Current Approaches to Enhance In-Plane and Out-of-Plane Properties in Printed Parts

- Mixing nanomaterials in polymer filament

Advantage: Simple to enhance in-plane properties

Issues: Aggregation of Nano-fillers and defects in the filament resulting in poor properties in final part.

- Coating the filament

Advantage: Simple to enhance in-plane properties; Better control to reduce aggregation.

Issues: Aggregation around the raster affecting adhesion the rasters and layers.

Our Approach to Enhance the Strength of Printed Polymer Parts

Challenge

Controllable and Scalable techniques for stitching to avoid aggregation and poor adhesion

Background: Coating Glass Fibers with Cellulose Nanocrystals (CNCs)

CNC Effect on Interfacial Shear Strength

Background 1: Tensile and Flexural Properties of CNC-30GF/Epoxy Composites

Tensile Properties

- ↑ or – Modulus
- ↑ or – Strength
- ↑ or – Strain at break

Flexural Properties

- ↑ Modulus
- ↑ Strength
- – Strain at break

What is Cellulose?

Moon et al. Chem. Soc. Rev. 2011; 40, 3941

Cellulose Nanoparticles

Mechanical Properties:

- Tensile Strength: 2-7.5 GPa
- Elastic Modulus: 120-220 GPa

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Tensile Strength (GPa)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)
CNs	1.6	2 - 7.5	120-220
Pulp Fiber	0.8-1.2	0.3-1.4	5-45
Kevlar-49 fiber	1.4	3.5	124-130
Glass fiber	1.5	4.8	86
Carbon fiber	1.8	1.5 - 5.5	150-500
Steel Wire	7.8	4.1	210
Carbon Nanotubes	--	11-63	270-950

Thermal:

- Expansion: $4-6 \times 10^{-6}/K$
- Degradation: 200-300 C

Our Setup at TAMU – Atomization System

Our Setup at TAMU – 3D Printing

Our Setup at TAMU

Quality of Dispersion/Distribution of CNC by Spraying

Tensile Properties

Interlayer Shear Strength Properties

Addition of 0.5 wt% CNC results in 15% and 44% increase in ILSS of LD and TD samples, respectively. This is particularly important as separation of layers is the main reason for the low strength values of 3D printed polymer parts. Enhancement of ILSS in this case can be due to the adhesive effect of CNC on adjacent layers. The adhesion effect of CNC is higher for TD samples suggesting that this effect improves the interlayer adhesion in weak samples better than strong samples.

CNC Content on Printed Parts

The CNCs wt% within the printed samples are correlated with their concentration in the sprayed aqueous suspension as shown in this plot. The neat ABS samples are used as the baseline for determining the CNC content. The plot also shows the thermal decomposition behavior of neat and CNC-ABS samples. Weight loss for CNC-ABS samples starts at $\sim 250^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is corresponding to the degradation temperature of CNC, indicating that CNC has been deposited on the ABS.

Fracture Surface Morphology - Transverse Direction

Fracture Surface Morphology - Longitudinal Direction

Deteriorating
effect of CNC

Fracture Surface Morphology – Interlayer Adhesion

Effect of Water – Was it evaporated?

Spaying pure water (without CNC) on the LD samples and comparing the properties with those of the neat ABS samples showed no difference in the tensile properties, and thus disproved the assumption that incomplete evaporation is the main cause for stiffness reduction.

Conclusion

1. Assessing the thermo-mechanical properties and interlayer adhesion of CNC-ABS samples indicated that spraying the aqueous suspension of CNC with 0.5-1 wt% concentrations significantly improved the tensile strength of both longitudinal and transverse printed ABS samples by 33%, the tensile modulus by 20%, and the interlayer shear strength by 44%.

2. Increasing CNC concentration above 1 wt% results in agglomerates between layers, which negatively affects the interlayer bonds and consequently reduces the strength.